

Design of a High Performance Dual Arm Aerial Manipulator

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Abstract. This paper presents the design of a dual arm aerial manipulation robot consisting of a customized hexarotor platform equipped with a lightweight dual arm manipulator. The proposed design is intended to integrate multiple devices required for building a complete aerial manipulation system, including vision and range sensors, on-board computers, communication devices, navigation systems, along with the manipulator. The developed platform will provide optimum performance in terms of flight time and payload taking into account the current technology available for building these kind of aircrafts. The design of the platform also considers vibration isolation, control and stability, and extended workspace for the manipulator. A lightweight (1.8 kg) and human-size dual arm manipulator has been integrated in the developed platform. Each arm provides 5 degrees of freedom (DOF) for end effector positioning and orientation. The arms are built using smart servo actuators and a frame structure manufactured in anodized aluminum. The design is validated through rigidity and modal analysis using finite element methods (FEM). The developed platform has been tested in outdoor flights, evaluating the influence of arms motion over the stability of the platform.

Keywords: Aerial Manipulation, Multicopter Design, Dual Arm Manipulator.

1 Introduction

The integration of one or multiple [1] robotic arms in an aerial platform allows the execution of several inspection and maintenance tasks in areas and workspaces out of the reach or with high risk for human operators. Some representative scenarios include high altitude pipes in chemical plants, polluted facilities, high voltage towers, or wind turbines. Traditionally, the access to specific points in these areas required the deployment of scaffoldings or manned helicopters, but the cost of these alternatives may be prohibitive for many sectors in the industry, especially if the inspection and maintenance tasks have to be performed periodically. On top of that, an aerial manipulation robot can be autonomous enough to perform typical tasks by itself without requiring additional elements which tend to increase the cost of the operations.

Vertical Take-Off and Landing (VTOL) remotely piloted aircraft systems (RPAs) such as multirotors [2][3] or helicopters [4][5] are suitable platforms for building an aerial manipulation robots due to their capability to hover in the air, meanwhile the robotic arms are executing their task. Despite the high payload capacity provided by autonomous helicopters, capable to carry a 7-DOF industrial manipulator [4], the current trend in aerial manipulation is to integrate very low weight robotic arms (<1 kg) over multirotor platform, as the cost and complexity of quadrotors and hexarotors is significantly lower than in a helicopter. On the one hand, helicopters are usually powered by combustion engines, because of the high torque demanded by the main rotor, especially when heavy payloads are involved. Internal combustion engines produce an inherent vibration that tends to complicate the control of the manipulator and the platform itself. On the other hand, a multirotor divides the total load between all its rotors, so each propeller needs less torque than an equivalent helicopter would require. Electrical motors are compound of less moving parts, which results in less vibrations compared to fuel engines. In addition, they have simpler mechanisms, simplifying the maintenance and repair.

Most of the aerial manipulation systems that can be found are still research prototypes integrating a customized multilink manipulator [6] – [8] developed for a specific platform. Bimanual manipulation has been considered only in a few works. Valve turning is demonstrated in [9] with a quadrotor equipped with two simple 2-DOF manipulators. A highly dexterous human-size dual arm manipulator is tested in outdoors in [10], whereas reference [2] presents an anthropomorphic, compliant and lightweight dual arm. It is necessary to remark that commercially available multirotor platforms are not designed for integrating robotics arms [3], which may have implications in the performance. A commercial platform might not be suitable for coupling the robotic arms, or allocating them properly to maximize their operation space. A platform designed specifically for a dedicated payload and operation requirements will have a better performance in terms of weight, size, control and flight time.

The main contribution of this paper is the design of a hexarotor platform intended to long endurance, bimanual aerial manipulation operations in outdoors. The platform, weighting 22 kg, provides up to 20 minutes flight time with 8 kg payload, allowing the integration of multiple sensors and devices necessary for building an aerial manipulation robot. The paper also covers the design and development of a human size, lightweight and low inertia dual arm manipulator developed from the scratch at the Robotics, Vision and Control Group of the University of Seville. The design of the hexarotor is validated in simulation using FEM analysis over the CAD model. Preliminary flight tests have been conducted in outdoors for analyzing the influence of arms motion over the aerial platform.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces some design concepts related to aerial manipulation (aerial platform and robotic arms). Section III presents the proposed design of the hexarotor platform, while Section IV is focused on the design of the lightweight dual arm manipulator. Section V presents the simulation and experimental results of the developed aerial platform, the arms, and the integrated system, presenting the conclusion of this work in Section VI.

2 Design Considerations in Aerial Manipulation

2.1 Design of multirotor platforms

The reduction of the total lifting weight is one of the most important aspects to consider during the design of a multirotor platform. A lightweight vehicle needs less lifting force, so less energy is consumed, and thus the flight time is increased. The reduction of weight should be present during the design of any involved part of the aerial platform, such as the propulsion system, the frame structure, the energy storage (e.g. batteries or fuel), the on-board electronics, the payload, etc. More functionalities typically involve more devices, and as minimal as they may be, they still add weight to the platform. To achieve the minimum weight, only the most necessary functionalities should be kept. In fact, it is desirable that the aerial manipulator provides a certain level of flexibility in the integration of devices, in such a way that the user can add or remove specific components according to the intended application.

It typically results convenient to reduce the size of the platform, and in aerial manipulation it is imposed as an additional requirement. A smaller size vehicle facilitates its navigation in an environment with obstacles, also reducing the interferences between the manipulator and the platform itself, and a better interaction with the environment. The main structure of the platform should be resistant enough to stand all the forces across it. These forces are mainly associated to the propulsion system and the weight of the platform. Carbon fiber and aluminum are widely used in aircrafts due to its properties of low weight and high resistance. Legal aspects should be taken into account regarding the weight of the platform. AESA [13] establishes a Maximum Take-Off Weight (shorten as MTOW) of 25 kg. If the platform exceeds this weight, a Certificate of Airworthiness is then needed.

There are many parameters involved in the selection of the right propeller. A detailed analysis of the behavior of propellers is seen more onwards. Brushless motors are nowadays widely used in multicopters due to their high efficiency, less electronic noise, higher speeds, and because they are more reliable and light than fuel engines. The electrical energy is stored in lithium polymer batteries, abbreviated as LiPo, characterized by their high specific energy (energy per unit of mass) and discharge capacity. Note that the brushless motors may demand continuous current greater than 100 A. Alternatively, lithium-ion (Li-Ion) batteries are an interesting alternative to consider, as they have even higher gravimetric power densities than LiPo batteries, although these cannot provide high power outputs in short periods of time.

The stability and maneuverability of a multirotor will depend on the disposition of the elements in the platform, which defines the distribution of weight and thus the rotational inertias along the tree axis. Tilted rotors may be considered, as they can increase the maneuverability of the platform. Rotors can be tilted a slight angle facing to each other, which improves maneuverability in yaw, and another slight angle towards the center of the platform, which improves maneuverability in roll and pitch.

2.2 Design of lightweight manipulators

The design of robotic arms intended to aerial manipulation applications is a complex task due to the multiple and demanding requirements imposed by the aerial platform in terms of low weight and inertia, mechanical robustness, dexterity and velocity. On the one hand, the mass of the manipulator should not be above half the maximum payload for preventing that the rotors are damaged due to overload and the maneuverability is affected. It is also convenient that most part of the mass of the manipulator, which typically corresponds to the actuators, is placed close to the base of the multirotor for reducing as much as possible the reaction forces/torques caused by the dynamic coupling with the aerial platform. This can be achieved using transmission mechanisms such like bars, timing belts or pulleys. In practice, the low inertia feature simplifies the control and improves the positioning accuracy during the aerial manipulation operation. On the other hand, the weight constraint has immediate implications over the choice of the actuators, and thus, over the maximum load that the arms can handle. The so called smart servos (Herkulex, Dynamixel) are nowadays the most extended solution for building lightweight manipulators due to their high torque to weight ratio and because these actuators integrate the motor, gearbox, control electronics and communications in a compact device that can be easily assembled into a frame structure. However, these actuators present important technological limitations that may affect the implementation of controllers, as there is no torque feedback or control, the bandwidth is low (<100 Hz), and the embedded servo controller has to be interfaced. The torque required by the servos will be determined by the maximum desired lift load and by the expected weight of the manipulator itself. Considering the typical upper arm-forearm configuration, the higher torque is associated to the flexion and extension motions at the shoulder and elbow joints.

The kinematic configuration of the manipulator is determined by the intended application in the first place, although the limitation in the payload may require a reduction in the number of actuators if necessary. Regarding the kinematics, it is convenient to consider a shoulder-elbow-wrist joint structure with the corresponding upper arm and forearm links, imposing that all the joint axes intersect in a common point. In this way the equations of the forward/inverse kinematic model result in a more simple form. The design of the frame structure of the manipulator is usually the most complicated part. The structure supports the actuator and the rotation of the links, isolating the actuators against radial/axial loads and impacts. The appropriate choice of the material is determined by the low weight and robustness requirements. Plastic parts should be avoided, as ABS or PLA plastics used by 3D printers are not impact resistant enough. Note that during the physical interaction between the aerial manipulator and the environment, the robotic arm will support the mechanical energy of the whole platform. Aluminum and carbon fiber are well suited materials due to their low mass density (2.75 vs 1.6 g/cm³) and high mechanical resistance. Aluminum is however preferred mainly because its low cost material and because it is easily malleable, allowing the manufacturing of L-shaped and U-shaped frame parts simply bending the flat profile sections. Note that these geometries are necessary for building kinematic chains with orthogonal joint axes.

3 Design of Hexarotor Platform

A rendered view of the multirotor design can be seen in **Fig. 1**. The following section justifies the chosen design by considering the aspects previously described in Section II. The design requirements justify the geometry and the distribution of elements within the platform. The frame structure analyzes the loads it has to handle, the design of the pieces and the chosen materials. The propulsion system describes the process of selection of the right propellers, motors and batteries, so maximum performance is achieved.

Fig. 1. Concept design of the hexarotor platform.

3.1 Design Requirements

The proposed design satisfies two basic requirements regarding the autonomy and payload capacity. A flight time of 20 minutes for a maximum payload of 8 kg is desired. The payload may include the dual arm manipulator, onboard computer, perception sensors (cameras, LIDAR, ...) and communication devices. Note that this design is intended to integrate multiple devices required for building an aerial manipulation robot. It was also imposed that the size of the platform, defined as the distance from tip to tip of the blades, is as small as possible. The separation of the legs of the landing gear is determined by the dimensions of the dual arm manipulator. Special effort has been put on maximizing the workspace of the manipulator, avoiding collisions with the frame of the UAV. A flat configuration is used, where rotors do not interfere with each other. It is preferable, since the air flow each rotor sees is clean, so the propulsion is more efficient and the result is a better flight time. Instead, a coaxial configuration of rotors could be considered, but it has been discarded in this design, as it introduces power losses and thus less efficiency is achieved. Batteries, payload, electronics, and most elements are disposed in the middle of the platform, so most of the weight is concentrated in the center. By this, it is reduced the mass moment of inertia of the vehicle, allowing for better maneuverability.

3.2 Frame Structure

The frame structure has been manufactured by Drone Tools [12], most part of it in carbon fiber due to its properties of high resistance and low weight. However, it is not easy to achieve complex geometries with this material. Carbon fiber sheets and tubes are commercially available in many thicknesses and lengths. Therefore, the use of this material is restricted to planar shapes and cylinders, so it can be bought in pieces and cut as desired. When more complex geometries are needed at some places of the structure, other materials are used to fulfill every particular task. Aluminum is widely employed in aircraft structure frames, due to its low mass density, high strength and ease of manufacture. This material results more suitable for manufacturing frame parts with complex geometries, such as joints between different parts (motor stands, tube joints to the central plate) or stiffeners in the central plate. Nuts and bolts are made of steel to ensure rigidity in punctual joints. 3D printed plastic is useful for customizing some pieces, and it is used in areas where there are no exigent structural loads, such as cases for on-board devices to isolate them from wind and dust. The chart below presents the weight each element adds to the platform.

Fig. 2. Frame structure and propulsion system weight chart (kg / pct.)

3.3 Propulsion System

Thrust should be high enough to stand the weight of the platform, which is 22 kg of vertical thrust. Maximum efficiency should be achieved in order to reduce the energy consumption, so the flight time is extended as much as possible. Larger propellers allow for better thrust and efficiency, but the size of the platform is then increased. For this reason, three-bladed propellers are used, as they allow for greater thrust within the same propeller diameter, and thus reducing the platform maximum length. To guarantee a reliable performance, only high-end products from recognized brands are considered. KDEDirect is a well-known manufacturer of high-end motors for RPAS, and the main components of the propulsion (propellers, brushless motors and ESCs) are supplied by this brand. The manufacturer provides performance testing data for different combinations of motor and propellers, such as voltage supply, power input, generated thrust, rotational speed and efficiency, among others. The selection of the most suitable elements for the propulsion system is based upon this data. The specifications of the developed propulsion system have been summarized on **Table 1**. The resulting flight time is about 20 minutes with a total payload of 8 kg.

Table 1. Propulsion System Specifications.

Propellers		Brushless Motors	
Diameter	21.5''	Model	KDE6213XF-185
Pitch	7.3''	Kv	185 rpm/V
Number of blades	3	Rotor/Stator Poles	28/24
Material	Carbon Fiber	Diameter	70 mm
Foldable	Yes	Length	39 mm
Weight	85 g	Weight	415 g
Brand	KDEDirect	Brand	KDEDirect
Electronic Speed Controller		Batteries	
Model	UAS75HVC	Capacity	16000 mAh
Refresh Rate	600 Hz	Voltage	22.2V
Maximum Current	75 A (180 seg)	Cell Wiring	6S1P
Internal BEC	None	Discharge Rate	15 C
Size	82x37 mm	Weight	1985 g
Weight	114 g	Size	190x73x62 mm
Brand	KDEDirect	Brand	Tattu

3.4 Developed Platform

A picture of the developed dual arm aerial manipulator can be seen in **Fig. 3**. The aerial platform is a hexarotor manufactured by Drone Tools according to the design specifications indicated above. The frame structure is built in carbon fiber, using aluminum parts for assembling the motors of the propellers and the tubes of the arms and the landing gear to the central hub, where the autopilot is placed. The separation between the legs of the landing gear is such that the shoulder structure of the manipulator can be installed under the base, which is convenient for maintaining the symmetry in the mass distribution. As seen in **Fig. 3**, the manipulator is supported by a transversal carbon fiber tube attached to the vertical legs of the landing gear. The height of the shoulder structure with respect to the floor can be adjusted sliding this tube along the legs, although it is convenient that the height is minimum for reducing the interference of the landing gear in the workspace of the manipulator during the operation. The space left between the shoulder structure and the central hub of the platform can be used for integrating the rest of components of the aerial manipulator.

Fig. 3. Hexarotor platform manufactured by Drone Tools with the dual arm manipulator.

4 Lightweight and Human-size Dual Arm Manipulator

A picture of the developed dual arm manipulator can be seen in **Fig 4**. Each of the arms provides 5 DOF, three of them for end effector positioning, and two joints for wrist orientation. The kinematic configuration is similar to the one considered in the industrial manipulators: shoulder yaw at the base, followed by the shoulder pitch and elbow pitch joints, and the wrist roll and wrist pitch joints. The shoulder structure that supports both left and right arms consists of a pair of 370 mm length, 8×8 mm hollow square section aluminum profiles. The frame structure of the arms has been entirely manufactured by hand in anodized aluminum, using commercially available profiles, including 20×2 and 30×2 flat sections, and 8 mm Ø circular profiles. Aluminum is a well-suited material for building low weight manipulators intended to aerial applications due to their features: very low cost, low mass density (2.75 g/cm³) high mechanical resistance and malleability. The possibility of bending flat profiles for building L-shaped or U-shaped frames, results highly convenient for the design. In order to reduce the inertia of the arms, and thus the influence of arms motion over the aerial platform, most part of the weight of the arms corresponding to the actuators is placed closed to the shoulder structure. A parallel transmission mechanism has been employed for transmitting the motion of the elbow pitch servo to the elbow joint. Also the wrist roll servo is placed at the top of the forearm link, close to the elbow. The mass distribution and the representative lengths of the arms are represented in **Fig 4**.

Fig. 4. Developed prototype of lightweight and human size dual arm manipulator.

Besides the low weight and low inertia requirements, special attention has been paid in increasing the mechanical robustness and the protection of the servo actuators, as these represent around the 80% of the total cost in materials. A simple and low weight mechanism (~15 grams) has been integrated in the frame structure for isolating the shoulder yaw, elbow pitch and wrist roll servos against radial and axial loads that might damage their shaft due to high contact forces. The mechanism consists of a pair of igubal® EFOM-08 flange bearings screwed around the aluminum frame structure in a side-by-side configuration. The idea is that the radial and axial loads exerted over the joints are caught by the flange bearings and supported by the frame structure instead of exposing the servo actuators to them.

5 Results

5.1 FEM Analysis of the Frame Structure

To ensure the structural integrity of the multirotor, a FEM analysis of the frame structure was made. The main structure consists on the central plate and the tubes holding the motors. These parts bear the loads coming from the thrust generated by rotors, and the weight of the components allocated on the central plate (payload, batteries, electronics...). The proposed design structure under analysis is an optimized geometry which ensures structural integrity for minimal weight. Thanks to the symmetry of the multirotor, only a sixth part of the structure is simulated, and thus solving time and solution precision are improved.

Color graphics in **Fig. 5** present the results in displacements (left) and stresses (right). The simulation results correspond to a vertical-up load of 8 kg allocated at the free end of the tube. The 8 kg load is approximately the double of the nominal thrust generated by each rotor when at hovering. This excess of load represents the differences between the virtual idealized model and the real structure, where little imperfections may lead to failures. A distributed vertical-down load in the central plate simulates the weight of all the additional components. Carbon fiber sheets of 1,5 mm thickness is suffice for the main parts of the body. Aluminum stiffeners with 3 mm \emptyset and 50 mm tall are lightweight and allow to stand better the bending moments in the central plate. The carbon fiber tube is 30 mm \emptyset and 300 mm length.

Fig. 5. Results in displacements in meters (left) and stresses in pascals (right).

Colored deformations indicate the displacements of the structure once submitted to the loads. The maximum displacement of 2.8 mm occurs at the free extreme of the tube. Compared to the frame size, this displacement is negligible. For the stresses, a safe limit for the maximum stress is usually set at the elastic limit, from which permanent deformation (and possibly breakage) may occur. The maximum obtained stress is 179 MPa, which is under the elastic limit of carbon fiber and aluminum (600 MPa and 280 MPa, respectively). With these results, the structural integrity of the multirotor is ensured. The real platform built by DroneTools consist on a very similar geometry to the one simulated, although the carbon fiber plates have less holes to ensure rigidity and add reliability despite weight.

5.2 Outdoor Flight Tests

The developed manipulator has been validated through outdoor flight tests carried out within a $5 \times 5 \times 4$ meters space covered by a safety net. The intention was to analyze qualitatively the influence of arms motion over the stability of the hexarotor platform for different joint trajectories and speeds. A sequence of images taken from the video corresponding to this experiment is shown in **Fig. 8**. It is necessary to remark that the maximum deviation of the platform with respect to the initial position was less than one meter. This error is not too high taking into account that the multirotor was controlled in position using a GPS in a windy day, and that the DJI A3 autopilot treats the reaction forces/torques generated by the arms as a perturbation. In fact, the control of the multirotor is independent from the manipulator, as no feedback is provided to the autopilot relative to the state of the arms. A video of the experiments is shown in [11].

Fig. 6. Sequence of images corresponding to the outdoor flight tests.

The dual arm system includes an Odroid U3 computer board operated from a ground control station (GCS) through a 2.4 GHz WiFi link. A C/C++ program executed in this board takes care of generating the pre-defined trajectories, moving the arms to the take-off and landing positions, and logging the data from the servos. The position and speed of the shoulder and elbow servos during a certain time interval is depicted in **Fig. 9**. Despite of the high joint velocities (up to 285 deg/s) generated by the servo actuators, it was found that the influence of arms motion over the positioning accuracy is relatively low due to the low weight and inertia of the manipulator.

Fig. 9. Joints position and velocity of left and right arms during the outdoor flight test.

6 Conclusion

This paper has detailed the design of a dual arm aerial manipulator with extended flight time (up to 20 minutes) and payload (up to 22 kg). The proposed design has been validated through outdoor flight tests. Experimental results show that, qualitatively, the high-speed motions performed by the lightweight arms do not significantly disturb the aerial platform when a standard industrial autopilot is employed.

As future work, an integrated control system for the dual arm aerial manipulator will be developed, so the reaction forces/torques generated by the arms can be estimated and compensated by the autopilot and the positioning accuracy is improved. The developed platform is designed to integrate multiple perception and navigation sensors, including cameras, LIDAR, range sensors or DGPS, necessary for the execution of complex aerial manipulation tasks.

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